

**SEPARATION AND OPTIMIZATION OF PHENOLIC COMPONENT
FROM *ANACARDIUM OCCIDENTALES* TESTA BY SOLVENT
EXTRACTION METHOD**

Lenin Kumar B*, Lokeswari N¹ and Sri Rami Reddy D²

*Research Scholar, Department of Biotechnology, Dr. B.R.Ambedkar University, Etcherla,
Srikakulam Dist., AndhraPradesh, India.

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Biotechnology, Dr. B.R.Ambedkar University, Etcherla,
Srikakulam Dist., AndhraPradesh, India.

²Professor, Centre for Biotechnology, Department of Chemical Engineering, Andhra
University, AndhraPradesh, India.

Article Received on
23 October 2014,

Revised on 16 Nov 2014,
Accepted on 07 Dec 2014

***Correspondence for
Author**

Lenin Kumar B

Research Scholar,
Department of
Biotechnology, Dr.
B.R.Ambedkar
University, Etcherla,
Srikakulam Dist.,
AndhraPradesh, India.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to investigate tannins by using a process for utilizing the waste raw material (*Anacardium occidentales L. testa*) into a useful substance. Tannins are the fourth most abundant plant constituent after cellulose, hemicelluloses and lignin. For separation of tannins, water was used as solvent. Optimization parameters time, temperature and particle size was studied for optimum extraction of tannins from cashew waste testa. During the experiment samples were stored in the absence of heat in a dark container. Moisture content of the samples was estimated.

KEYWORDS: *Anacardium occidentales L.*, solvent, optimization, tannins and testa.

INTRODUCTION

Tannins are naturally occurring polyphenolic compounds with varying molecular weights that occur naturally in the plant kingdom. (Esmail Zakipour-Molkabadi *et.al.* 2013) These phenolic compounds differ from others by having the ability to precipitate proteins from solutions. In the plant kingdom these tannins are found in leaves, bark and wood. Tannins are considered to be the plants secondary metabolic products because they play no direct role in

the plants metabolism. After lignin, tannins are the second most abundant group of plant phenolics.

The existence of tannins in the leaves of 46 different species of fodder trees and stated that generally tree leaves and browse contain both types of tannins (hydrolysable and condensed) (Kumar and Vaithyanathan 1990). The main families of dicotyledons, which contain tannins include Aceraceae, Actinidiaceae, Anacardiaceae, Bixaceae, Burseraceae, Combretaceae, Dipterocarpaceae, Ericaceae, Grossulariaceae and Myricaceae while those of monocotyledons include Najadaceae and Typhaceae. (Joseck Olukusi Alwala *et.al.* 2014). Tannins are present in large number of feed and forages. The formation of complexes of tannins with nutrients, such as carbohydrates, proteins and minerals, has negative effects on their utilization. (Hina Iqbal and Ashima Kapoor. 2012). The present works describes the extraction of hydrolysable tannins from waste testa.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Substrate: *Anacardium occidentale* L. (Cashew testa) was collected from the cashew industries in Palasa (Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh) and Visakhapatnam (Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh) and placed in cold and dark containers.

Extraction of tannins: Testa of the *Anacardium occidentale* was used for the extraction of tannins. Testa were dried and milled using ball mill to get the particle size below 5.0 mm. Water is preferred as solvent in view of its high saturation limit of the dissolved solids, inherent safety and ease of separation. Water should be soft and should not be contain iron.

Braemer's test: For the identification of tannins present, to 2ml of aqueous extract 2ml of 5% FeCl₃ was added. Formation of yellow brown or greenish black precipitate indicates that tannins are present (Jigna and Sumitra. 2007., Rajyalaxmi M.R. and Sindhu A. 2011., Manjula *et.al.* 2013).

Effect of time: For achieving maximum degree of tannin extraction, the effect of time was studied by varying the time period between 15 min to 50 min.

Effect of Temperature: Different temperatures (20°C - 90°C) were used for optimization of the temperature for maximum extraction of tannin.

Effect of Particle size

The effect of particle size of the tannin resource cashew testa was studied by varying the particle size between 0.2 mm to 5.0 mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Samples were analysis before extraction of polyphenolic component, contents present in the sample were moisture content 35% - 39%, tannins 28% - 35%, soluble non- tans 15% - 10%, pH of standard tan liquor from testa 3.5, colour dark black or brown. After drying the sample moisture content was estimated 7% - 8%.

To determine optimal operational conditions, an experimental survey was conducted for extracting tannin materials from *Anacardium occidentale* testa (0.5 particle size) with 5% (w/v) water – immiscible solvent. Braemers's test was performed for the aqueous extract. Yellow brown of greenish black colour precipitate was formed and tannins present in the test sample were confirmed. The percentage of extracted tanning materials from samples was measured by varying the following factors: time, temperature and particle size.

Effect of Time: The effect of time on tannin extraction was studied by varying time periods between 15- 50 min. with 0.5mm particle size substrate at 35°C.

Table1: Effect of time on tannin extraction

Time period (min.)	Tannin (mg/ml)
15	3.72
20	3.81
25	3.94
30	4.10
40	4.72
45	4.32
50	3.91

The optimum time period for maximum tannin extraction was 40 min. Extraction of tannins has increased with increase in time up to 40 minutes, with further increase in time decreased tannins content.

2. Effect of temperature: Effect of temperature on tannin extraction was studied in different temperature range 30°C - 60°C and used particle size 0.5mm substrate for 40 min.

Table 2: Effect of temperature on tannin extraction.

Temperature (°C)	Tannin (mg/ml)
30	4.22
35	4.24
40	4.19
45	3.92
50	3.81
55	3.71
60	3.10

Temperature 35 °C was optimum for extraction of 4.24mg/ml of tannin. Increasing temperature decreases concentration of tannin and it promotes hydrolysis and unwanted extraction of hemicelluloses and cellulose materials.

3. Effect of particle size: Effect of particle size on tannin extraction was carried out by using substrate of different particle sizes (0.2mm, 0.5mm, 1.0mm, 3.0mm and 5.0mm) at 35°C for 40 min. to determine the effect of particle size on testa tannin extraction for achieving high extraction efficiency.

Table 3: Effect of particle size on tannin extraction

Particle size (mm)	Tannin (mg/ml)
Fine powder	3.10
0.2	3.81
0.5	4.86
1.0	4.73
3.0	4.32
5.0	4.27

Fine powder substrate gives less tannin extract. The particle size 0.5mm substrate gives high tannin content. As the particle size decreases, more surface area will be available for tannin extraction and increase in tannin extraction was obtained. Optimum particle size is found to be 0.5mm (**Table 3**).

Madhunisha *et.al.* 2013 studied 300-1400µm average particle size of guava leaves. Lokeswari and Sujatha . 2011 reported optimum particle size 0.5mm for extraction of tannins from Divi Divi pods. This is similar to present obtained results.

However, from grinding energy and product purification cost points of view, fine grinding is not favored. Further investigating of tannins conversion was not shown in this paper.

REFERENCES

1. Esmail Zakipour-Molkabadi, Zohreh Hamidi-Esfahani, Mohammad Ali Sahari and Mohammad Hosein Azizi. 2013. A New Native Source of Tannase Producer, *Penicillium* sp. EZ-ZH190: Characterization of the Enzyme. *Iranian Journal of Biotechnology*, 2013; 11(4): 244-50.
2. Hina Iqbal and Ashima Kapoor. 2012. Culture Conditions for the Production of Tannase from *Trichoderma harzianum* MTCC 10841. *Intr. Jnl. of Sci. and Tech*, 2012; 1(11): 584 -595.
3. Joseck Olukusi Alwala, Francis Ndilu Kiema and Wycliffe Wanzala. 2014. Determination of tannin concentrations in African indigenous vegetables, grains and cassava roots from Emuhaya district, western Kenya. *Americal jnl. of nutri. and food sci*, 2014; 1(1): 1-8.
4. Jigna P and Sumitra VC. 2007. In vitro antimicrobial activity and phytochemical analysis of some Indian medicinal plant. *Turk. J. Biol.* 2007; 31: 53-58
5. Kumar R. and Vaithyanathan S. 1990. Occurrence, nutritional significance and effect on animal productivity of tannins in tree leaves. *Animal Feed Science and Technology*. 1990; 30: 21-38.
6. Lokeswari N and Sujatha P. 2011. Isolation of tannins from *Caesalpinia coriaria* and effect of physical parameters. *Intr. research Jnl. of pharmacy*. 2011; 2(2): 146 -152.
7. Madhunisha G.V, Dhasarathan P and Sankaranarayanan S. 2013. Production and optimization of thermostable tannase from *Aspergillus niger* using agricultural residues. *Global J. of Engg. & Appl. Sciences*. 2013; 3(2): 88-92.
8. Manjula K.T, J.M.Sasi Kumar and V.K.Gopalakrishnan. 2013. The phytochemical screening and profiling of biochemical parameters in different parts of *Pandanus unipapillatus* Dennst. In South India. *World Jnl. of pharmac. Research*. 2013; 2(4): 878-889.
9. Rajyalaxmi M.R. and Sindhu A. 2011. Preliminary phytochemical screening and antioxidant activity of an ayurvedic formulation: Balarishtam. *Intr. Jnl. of research in ayurveda and pharmacy*. 2011; 2(6): 1645 – 1647.